

Notes

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of Thorium(IV) Complexes with Potentially Tetradentate Schiff Bases

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Synthesis and characterisation of thorium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases (1–4) derived from thiocarbohydrazide and substituted salicylaldehydes are described.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are light yellow in colour and sparingly soluble in common organic solvents, but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The elemental analyses (Table 1) show that the complexes have 1:1 stoichiometry. The conductance measurements in DMF are too low to account for any dissociation of the complexes in DMF. Hence, the complexes may be regarded as non-electrolytes. The molecular weights of these complexes could not be determined because of their insoluble nature in nitrobenzene.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Th^{IV} COMPLEXES

Sl. no.*	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		Metal	N	S
1.	Th(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S)(NO ₃) ₂	34.92	12.62	4.81
		(34.73)	(12.57)	(4.79)
2.	Th(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S)(NO ₃) ₂	34.01	12.32	4.61
		(33.33)	(12.06)	(4.59)
3.	Th(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S)(NO ₃) ₂	32.02	11.68	4.40
		(31.87)	(11.53)	(4.39)
4.	Th(C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ SCl ₂)(NO ₃) ₂	31.89	11.42	4.32
		(31.48)	(11.39)	(4.34)

* Indicates complex with the corresponding ligand numbers 1–4.

All the complexes exhibit a broad ir band of medium intensity around 3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH). The band due to hydrogen bonded OH appearing at 2 630–2 675 cm⁻¹ in the ligand disappears in the

complexes. The high intensity band due to phenolic C–O around 1 280 cm⁻¹ appears at 1 300–1 330 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, supporting the involvement of OH groups in the complex formation. Another medium intensity band due to the phenolic C–O stretch appearing around 1 520 cm⁻¹ in the ligands, shows a high frequency shift of the order of 10–15 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes ruling out the bridging probability¹. The band appearing at 1 610–1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=N) is shifted to 1 600–1 610 cm⁻¹, suggesting coordination of C=N groups to the metal ion through nitrogens. The ν_{C–S} band does not show any perturbation in the complexes. The band at 1 240–1 260 cm⁻¹ is attributed to coordinated nitrate group². In these complexes, the ν_{M–N} and ν_{M–O} bands have been assigned at 450–545 and 440–460 cm⁻¹ respectively, in view of previous assignments³. These observations focus upon the tetradentate behaviour of the ligands (1–4).

The electronic spectra of the complexes in solution showed no distinct bands in the region 330–750 nm.

The pmr spectra have been studied for only two representative complexes namely with ligands 1 and 2. The spectra of the ligands consist of signals due to azomethine (δ 8.3 ppm), *o*-hydroxy (12.3), amino (7.5) and phenyl (6.72–7.20) protons. In addition to these signals, a signal obtained at δ 3.15 for ligand 2 is attributed to the methyl proton. These observations suggest that these ligands exist in the phenolimine form⁴.

In the thorium(IV) complexes, the signal due to the *o*-hydroxy proton of the ligand disappears indicating that the complexation of the ligand occurs through deprotonation. The proton signals due to =CH groups appear downfield (δ 8.55 ppm) due to deshielding. The NH protons appear along with the aromatic protons range. These results provide support for the ir inferences.

The results suggest that Th^{IV} exhibits coordination number six in these complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. The substituted salicylaldehydes⁵, thiocarbohydrazide⁶ and the ligands⁷ were prepared according to reported methods.

Thorium(IV) complexes :

Thorium(IV) nitrate (0.01 mol) was refluxed with thiocarbohydrazone (0.01 mol) in ethanolic medium for ~ 3 h. The precipitation of the complex was initiated by adding water. The complex was filtered and washed thoroughly with water containing a little alcohol, then with ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 .

Thorium content in complexes was determined by gravimetry* as ThO_2 . Nitrogen was determined by Dumas' method and sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as the sulphate after oxidising with fuming nitric acid.

Conductance was measured with an Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge using DMF as solvent. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer IR-297 spectrophotometer, far-ir spectra on a Polytec FIR-30 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal reference and DMSO as solvent.

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